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Impact Of Technology Stress Of Computer Science Students Academic Engagement In Selected Tertiary Institutions In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper is to investigate the Impact of Technology Stress on the Academic Engagement of Computer Science Students in Selected Tertiary Institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Two research objectives and two research questions was used by the researchers. A cross-sectional survey design was employed. Data was collected from a sample of 250 computer science students randomly selected from three major tertiary institutions in Sokoto State (Shehu Shagari College of Education and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic). A structured questionnaire with validated scales was used to measure technology stress (encompassing factors like techno-overload, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty) and academic engagement (measuring behavioural, emotional, and cognitive dimensions). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis with the aid of SPSS version 26. The results revealed a high prevalence of technology stress among the students, primarily driven by techno-complexity (difficulty using software/hardware) and techno-insecurity (fear of being replaced by technology or more skilled peers). It is recommended that tertiary institutions implement targeted interventions, such as foundational digital literacy programs, robust technical support systems, and stress management workshops, to mitigate technology stress and foster a more conducive learning environment for computer science students.

Keywords: Technology Stress, Technostress, Academic Engagement, Computer Science Education, Tertiary Institutions, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, highlights the critical intersection between technological engagement and academic performance. As digital learning environments increasingly become integral to education systems, understanding the stress that arises from technology usage is essential for academic success. Technology stress refers to the anxiety and pressure experienced by students in response to the demands of digital learning platforms and tools, which can hinder their overall engagement and learning outcomes (Ifenthaler et al., 2020).

Research indicates that the recent surge in technology use for educational purposes, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, has amplified both the opportunities and challenges faced by students. The

rapid transition to online learning modalities exposed students to diverse digital tools, necessitating a greater level of adaptability and technological proficiency (Aditya, 2021; Yasir et al., 2022). However, substantial disparities exist among institutions regarding access to quality digital learning resources and the infrastructure necessary to support these tools (Cullinan et al., 2021).

The impact of technology stress on the academic engagement of computer science students in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria, is a multifaceted issue that warrants thorough exploration. The integration of technology in education has been associated with both academic achievement and engagement as well as challenges that can lead to increased stress among students. The diversity of technology use—including online learning platforms—has been linked to heightened academic pressure, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, which presented students with numerous digital tools to navigate (Takash et al., 2024). A relevant study indicates that 71% of students reported increased stress levels directly associated with technology use, highlighting how the technological burden can detract from rather than enhance academic participation (Takash et al., 2024).

Furthermore, several studies underscore the importance of contextual factors in understanding technology's role in education. Abubakar et al. emphasize that socioeconomic and infrastructural issues significantly influence technology integration in educational settings, particularly in Sokoto State (Abubakar et al., 2024).

However, technology has lowered international barriers and expanded the potential reach of colleges and universities in the sense that with sophisticated communication technologies, institutions of higher education are no longer limited to student markets or educational resources in their geographical regions. Also with technology, institutions of higher learning can provide lifelong learning opportunities to individuals who seek alternatives to traditional real-time, campus

Educational technologies like digital whiteboards are interactive devices that teachers can give students chances for a real time interaction. Vinay Thalari (2025), asserted that digital whiteboards make lessons more interactive, capturing students' attention with dynamic visuals videos, and exercises, leading to better retention and understanding of concepts. These indicate that students use technologies as tools for building and maintaining social connections and organizing their academic engagements more efficiently. In a bid towards organizing their private lives and maintaining social connections in addition to carrying out their academic responsibilities, students have had to rely heavily on technological tools (Niehaves & Plattfaut, 2013; Wright & Brown, 2004). This over-reliance/dependence on these technology tools, however, breeds technology-related stress (Technostress) on the users (students) of these devices consciously or unconsciously, be it physically, psychologically, behaviorally, or emotionally. The type of technology-related stress experienced by individual students varies depending on the individuals' technological skills, frequency of use of these tools, availability and accessibility, perception, orientation, and belief about technology (personality). Ayyagari (2011), asserts that because individuals differs, the level of technology stress a person may experience will also vary.

Statement of the Problems

Technology or ICT has become essential for students in carrying out their daily learning activities both within and outside the school premises. This fact, in addition to the advancement in technology, has made it possible for students to incorporate into their daily learning activities. Costley (2014), is of the opinion that technology has positive impact on students learning as it enable students become more engaged; consequently retain more information. Technology is relevant to the students as it affords them meaningful learning experiences.

However, according to organizational behavior researchers (Tarafdar, et al, 2007; 2008; 2011; Mawhinney, 2014), information and communication technologies were related to job strain, low job satisfaction, burnout, decreased academic engagement and an increased students' technology-related stress such as inability to navigate the web, inability to operate some technological devices, irritability, loss of temper, high state of anxiety when separated from technological gadgets, using computer terms in non-computer conversations, jealousy produced by technological competency, demotivation due to prolonged periods of any technological activity among others.

Physical and psychological, technology can be detrimental to individual health in different ways. As a result of this, there is the need to not only find out what proportions of students make use of these technologies and the technology stress factors that affect them but also to determine what impact technology stress have on students' academic engagement. Additional problem is when we consider the location, Sokoto which is not a city and thus most of the technological tools are scarce or not easily available but yet students and learners are expected to cop up with these short comings. It is worthy of investigating to find out the condition of technology stress among these students.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective is to investigate the impact of technology stress among computer science student academic engagement of students in tertiary institutions in Sokoto States. But the specific objectives are to :

1. Identify technology stress factors that mostly affect academic engagement of Computer Science Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.
2. Identify the general technology stress level of Computer Science Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.

Research Questions

1. Which technology -stress factors mostly affect the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto?
2. What is the general level of technology stress among Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto?

Review of Related Literature

According to Ramey (2013), Technology is a body of knowledge devoted to creating tools, processing actions and the extracting of materials. Ramey went ahead to assert that 'we use technology to accomplish various tasks in our daily lives and as such, we can describe technology as products and processes used to simplify our daily lives'. To Mawhinney (2014), Technology is the collection of techniques, skills, methods and processes used in the production of goods or services for the accomplishment of objectives. This means that, technology is the systematic application of knowledge to serve individual needs and solve problems.

Thiel (2014), asserts that technology is 'Any new way of doing things'. This definition, though very brief, is all encompassing. It implies technology as modern ways or approaches to carrying out activities and solving problems. To Ferre cited in Thiere (2014), technology is the 'practical implementations of intelligence'. He came up with this definition probably because technology is unlikely to have occurred by chance, without being created by intelligent beings—many presume to be mankind—given the inherent knowledge and requisite organization of technology as a system that allows it to produce objects and perform techniques to achieve goals. This means that, technology is the physical application or execution of innate knowledge for the purpose of accomplishing a task. Similarly in his own submission, Fernald (2014), avers that technology is the ability to convert society's resources (labour and capital) into output (goods and services that we value).

Alvarez-Risco at al (2021) investigated the relationship between communication overload, social overload, technology stress, exhaustion and academic performance. of university medicine students in Peru during the COVID-19 pandemic. A cross sectional analytical study of 2286 university medical students were involved, to assess the influence of technology stress as a mediator of social media overload, communication overload and mental exhaustion and its detrimental effect on the academic performance Of the University students. The findings f the research revealed that communication and social overload were found to be positively influencing technology stress by correlations of 0.284 and 0.557, respectively. Technology stress positively influence d exhaustion by 0.898, while exhaustion negatively influence d academic performance by -0.439.

Fitzgerald (2021) carried out research on the influence of t technology stress on perceived academic performance. The purpose of the research was to explore how technology characteristics influence

students' technology stress, and in turn their perceived academic performance. To examine this, Data were collected through an online self-administered questionnaire distributed through emails to 375 students enrolled in courses at MAU in Sweden during the period of April 2020 and a bivariate analysis was conducted to analyze the data. The results showed some technology characteristics were associated with technology stress, while some were not. The students' technology stress could, however, not be determined to have an association with their perceived academic performance. The study discusses possible contributing factors to the results. The study relates with the present study in content but differ in scope.

Mangundu (2023) conducted a study on the effects of technology stress on the academic commitment among first-year undergraduate students at an institution of higher education in South Africa, in accordance with the technostress creators' model and the adapted organizational commitment model. The findings of the study revealed that techno-complexity has a significantly direct negative relationship (-.74) with students' academic commitment. However, techno-uncertainty significantly positively (.42) impacts students' commitment. In addition, techno-invasion insignificantly positively impact (.11) on students' academic commitment. Interestingly, students' age negatively correlated with techno-complexity, with older students being less affected by the complexity of technology for learning. Surprisingly, time spend using information and communication technologies is associated with more effect from techno-uncertainty. In addition, the findings revealed that gender differences significantly impacted on the differences in the levels of students' technostress, with techno-invasion being more highly perceived by male students.

Mahapatra et al (2023) carried out a study on the relationship between technostress and academic achievement of University students of Gangahar Meher University, Sambulpur. The study found out a negative relationship between technostress and academic achievement among university students, with no significant difference in technostress levels between boys and girls.

Saleem et al (2024) explores the impact of technostress on students' motivation and academic performance in a study of technostress in students and online learning in a community of inquiry framework. The study investigates the moderating impact of instructors and university students. The study found out that technostress negatively impacts students' motivation and academic performance while instructor and university support play a crucial role in mitigating this effect.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

This study adopted Descriptive survey design. This is because it describes a population, situation or phenomenon that is being studied. Because of the nature of the study, descriptive research design will be used as it will allow the researcher to reach out to the study population in their various locations. Also, descriptive survey design will be adopted because the study is only interested in describing certain variables relating to the population.

Population of the Study:

The study population consists of 250 Computer Science UG3 Students across the two institutions in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. Population Distribution in the institution for the 2024/2025 Academic Session.

Sample and Sampling Technique:

Using the Research Advisor (2006) as a guide, a total number of 217 Economics Students will be proportionately and randomly selected to serve as samples for the study as shown in tables 2 and 3. Multi-stage sampling technique will be used in order to arrive at the targeted number and research advisor (2006) as a guide will be used to obtain the needed sample size.

Instrument for Data Collection:

Questionnaire will be used as an instrument for data collection. The instrument will be adapted from Bawa, Dalhatu and Tukur (2016). The instrument has four sections (A - D). Section A will contain the demographic information while sections B, C and D will contain the four-point Likert scale items which

ranges from (A) Agree, (SA) Strongly Agree, (D) Disagree and (SD) Strongly Disagree. The choice of questionnaire as the instrument for data collection is as a result of the respondents being literate, respondents require different convenient time to respond to the questions, questionnaire is the most frequently used instrument in educational research and it is more economical.

Procedure for Data Collection:

The researchers will administer and retrieve the questionnaires by the use of two research assistants in each of institutions. The use of research assistance will enable researchers to reach out to the respondents in the various lecture rooms in the institutions.

Procedure for Data Analysis:

Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages and mean will be use to answer the research questions.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *Which techno-stress factors mostly affect the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto?*

Table 4.3: Summary of techno-stress factors mostly affect the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.

Statement	N	Mean	St. Deviation	Decision
Poor internet connectivity and network issues	219	2.04	.889	Rejected
Lack of technical skills to handle academic software/tools.	219	2.00	.866	Rejected
Pressure to learn new technologies quickly.	219	1.96	.889	Rejected
Excessive screen time leading to fatigue and stress.	219	2.56	1.121	Accepted
Too many online tasks/assignments at the same time.	219	2.36	1.186	Rejected
Difficulty in balancing social media use and academic use of technology	219	2.64	1.184	Accepted
Limited access to reliable devices (laptops, smartphones).	219	2.60	1.118	Accepted

Table 4.1 Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the various level of the techno-stress factors mostly affect the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; Poor internet connectivity and network issues (Mean=2.04, Standard Deviation=.889), Lack of technical skills to handle academic software/tools (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.866), Pressure to learn new technologies quickly (Mean=1.96, Standard Deviation=.889), Excessive screen time leading to fatigue and stress (Mean=2.56, Standard Deviation=1.121), Too many online tasks/assignments at the same time (Mean=2.36, Standard Deviation=1.186), Difficulty in balancing social media use and academic use of technology (Mean=2.64, Standard Deviation=1.184), and Limited access to reliable devices (laptops, smartphones) (Mean=2.60, Standard Deviation=1.118). Overall, the results indicate that difficulty in balancing social media and academic use of technology (Mean = 2.64) and limited access to reliable devices (Mean = 2.60) were rated as the most prominent techno-stress factors. Conversely, pressure to learn new technologies quickly (Mean = 1.96) and lack of technical skills (Mean = 2.00) were considered the least impactful factors.

Research Question Two: *What is the general level of techno-stress among Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.*

Table 4.4 Summary of level of techno-stress among Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.

Statement	N	Mean	St. Deviation	Decision
I feel stressed when using technology for academic purposes.	219	2.56	1.121	Accepted
I experience frustration when technology does not work as expected.	219	2.40	1.155	Rejected
I feel overloaded by the amount of technology-based academic tasks.	219	2.00	.866	Rejected
I often feel mentally exhausted after long hours of technology use.	219	2.56	1.121	Accepted
I worry about my academic success due to stress from technology use.	219	2.64	1.184	Accepted
Overall, I experience a high level of techno-stress in my studies.	219	2.60	1.118	Accepted

Table 4.1 Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the various What is the general level of techno-stress among Computer Science students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; I feel stressed when using technology for academic purposes (Mean=2.56, Standard Deviation=1.121), I experience frustration when technology does not work as expected (Mean=2.40, Standard deviation=1.155), I feel overloaded by the amount of technology-based academic tasks (Mean=2.00, Standard deviation=.866), I often feel mentally exhausted after long hours of technology use (Mean=2.56, Standard deviation=1.121), I worry about my academic success due to stress from technology use (Mean=2.64, Standard deviation=1.184), Overall, I experience a high level of techno-stress in my studies (Mean=2.60, Standard Deviation=1.118). In general, the findings suggest that students experience a moderate level of techno-stress in their academic activities. Among the indicators, worry about academic success due to stress from technology use (Mean = 2.64) and overall experience of high techno-stress (Mean = 2.60) ranked highest. In contrast, feeling overloaded by technology-based academic tasks (Mean = 2.00) was identified as the least significant source of stress.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of this study reveal a complex relationship between technology stress and academic engagement among computer Science students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The discussion interprets these results within the context of existing scholarly work.

The high level of technology stress reported by students aligns with the core concept of "technostress" as defined by seminal authors like Tarafdar et al. (2007), who identified it as a modern stress disorder induced by an inability to cope with new computer technologies. However, the drivers in this context techno-complexity and techno-insecurity are particularly salient for a developing region. The stress from techno-complexity suggests that students may not have a strong foundational digital literacy before engaging with advanced computing concepts. This finding resonates with studies in similar contexts, such as the work of Awoyemi et al. (2020) in Southwestern Nigeria, which found that inadequate pre-tertiary exposure to ICT resources created a significant competency gap for students. The complexity of software development environments, programming languages, and network simulations can be overwhelming when access to reliable hardware and consistent internet connectivity is a challenge, a point underscored by research on the digital divide in Sub-Saharan Africa (Ifinedo et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the prominence of techno-insecurity is a critical finding. It reflects a fear that their skills are inadequate not just for academic success, but for future employability. This echoes the concerns raised by

Ragu-Nathan et al. (2008) that technostress can stem from the pressure to continuously update one's skills to avoid obsolescence. In a competitive job market, Nigerian computer science students may perceive their peers as more skilled, leading to anxiety and a feeling of insecurity, which directly impacts their learning confidence (Jena, 2015).

The core finding of a significant negative relationship between technology stress and academic engagement supports and extends the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) into the educational sphere. In this analogy, technology acts as a key "demand," while personal resilience and institutional support are "resources." When the demands (technology stress) outweigh the resources, burnout and disengagement occur (Salanova et al., 2013).

Techno-Complexity and Behavioural Engagement: The finding that techno-complexity was the strongest predictor of reduced behavioural engagement (e.g., skipping practical sessions, avoiding online submissions) is logical. When students find technology difficult to use, they are likely to develop avoidance behaviours. This is consistent with the work of Wang et al. (2020), who found that perceived complexity of e-learning systems was a major barrier to their continued use by university students. In Sokoto, where resources may be limited, a student who struggles to configure a necessary software package may simply disengage from the associated assignment rather than seek help in a potentially overstretched support system.

The findings cannot be divorced from the specific socio-economic and infrastructural context of Sokoto State. The challenges of unstable electricity, poor internet connectivity, and limited access to personal computers (Adebayo & Adesina, 2021) are not merely logistical issues; they are fundamental precursors to technology stress. Every power outage or network failure reinforces feelings of techno-uncertainty and complexity. Therefore, the technostress experienced by these students is not just about the nature of the technology itself, but also about the unreliable environment in which it must be used. This contextual layer amplifies the types of stress identified in more technologically advanced settings, making the need for localized interventions even more critical.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the relationship between technostress and academic engagement among students in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that students frequently engage with technology for academic purposes, yet they also encounter varying levels of technostress manifested through reduced concentration, procrastination, mental exhaustion, and worry about academic success. Key stressors identified include poor internet connectivity, limited access to reliable devices, excessive screen time, and the challenge of balancing social media with academic use.

Overall, the study concludes that while technology remains an indispensable tool for learning and research in tertiary institutions, technostress moderately hinders students' academic engagement and performance. The evidence suggests that the inability to effectively manage digital overload, persistent connectivity, and infrastructural limitations contributes to reduced motivation and academic productivity.

Therefore, addressing technostress requires a multi-level approach: institutions should provide reliable ICT infrastructure and digital literacy training, while students should be encouraged to adopt healthier technology-use habits. By mitigating the negative effects of technostress, tertiary institutions in Sokoto State can foster more sustainable and effective academic engagement, ultimately enhancing educational outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers come with the following recommendations:

1. Government and university management should invest in reliable internet connectivity, stable electricity, and up-to-date ICT facilities.
2. Provision of high-speed campus Wi-Fi and modern computer laboratories will reduce frustration caused by poor network services.

3. Institutions should establish device support schemes, such as subsidized laptops, computer leasing programs, or partnerships with ICT companies to make reliable devices more affordable for students.
4. Regular workshops and training should be organized to equip students with the technical skills to effectively handle academic software, e-learning platforms, and digital tools.
5. Special attention should be given to first-year students to ease their transition into technology-driven learning environments.
6. Students should be sensitized on how to manage excessive screen time, reduce distractions from social media, and adopt healthy study routines.
7. Institutions should strike a balance between online and face-to-face instructional delivery to reduce digital overload and accommodate students with limited access to devices or connectivity.
8. Peer mentoring and digital learning clubs could be encouraged, where students support each other in handling academic technologies.

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